

Project acronym:

RESINSURF

Project full title:

**Towards more RESilient, sustainable, competitive
and INTelligent electrochemical SURface treatments**

COMMUNICATION REPORT

1st part of the final communication deliverable

Delivery date: 31/12/2026

RECORD OF CHANGES

Version	Date	Description	Authors
1.0	07/05/2025	First version – Period 2024	CIDETEC

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. RESINSURF' S COMMUNICATION	4
2. PERIOD 1 (2024)	5
2.1. Introduction (2024)	5
2.2. Summary of main activities in 2024	5
2.2.1. Objective 1: Raising awareness on the environmental impact of electrochemical processes implying toxic substances such as Cr(VI) or critical raw materials. (+ RESINSURF's strategy)	6
2.2.2. Objective 2: Disseminating the advances of the pilots.	14
2.2.3. Objective 3: Disseminating the scientific results of the pilots.	17
2.3. Record of all the activities in 2024	18
3. CONCLUSIONS	26

1. RESINSURF'S COMMUNICATION

Table 1: Relationship between communication objectives and the channels used to transmit these messages according to target group. GT: Working group (Grupo de Trabajo) GT1: Promotion of the project's strategy and objectives. GT2: Presentation of the project's technical and scientific progress. GT3: Promotion of training and capacity-building activities.

Communication objective	GT	Target public	Main channels
1) Raising awareness on the environmental impact of electrochemical processes implying toxic substances such as Cr(VI) or critical raw materials.	GT1 Strategy	-General public -Sectoral agencies -Chambers of commerce -Business associations -Policy makers -Universities -Vocational training schools -Company workers	-Resinsurf's webpage -Youtube -Webinars -Linked In and X -Fairs -Professional press articles -Press advertisements
2) Disseminating the advances of the pilots .	GT2 Pilots	-SMEs -Large companies -Business associations	-Resinsurf's webpage -Professional press articles -Linked In and X (end)
3) Disseminating the scientific results of the pilots.	GT2 Pilots	-Universities -SMEs -Large companies -Business associations	-Resinsurf's webpage -Scientific publications -Fairs -Scientific congresses
4) Transferring the common strategy to adopt developed solutions.	GT3 Training and capacitation	-Universities -Vocational training schools -SMEs -Large companies -Business associations -Sectoral agencies	-Resinsurf's webpage -Webinars -Seminars -Workshops
5) Communicating the training activities, webinars and workshops.	GT3 Training and capacitation	-SMEs -Large companies -Universities -Vocational training schools -Business associations -Sectoral agencies	-Resinsurf's webpage -Linked In and X -Fairs -Press advertisements -Multipliers

2. Period 1 (2024)

2.1. Introduction (2024)

The RESINSURF project, coordinated by CIDETEC Surface Engineering, has carried out various communication activities in 2024 to promote chromium hexavalent-free (Cr(VI)) surface treatments in the industry. These initiatives have been essential for disseminating the project's objectives and progress, as well as raising awareness about the importance of adopting safer and more sustainable alternatives in industrial processes.

During this initial phase of the project, efforts have been focused on raising awareness of RESINSURF, its strategy, its objectives, and how these can provide benefits and solutions to the target audience.

Among the highlighted actions are publications in specialized media, including the inclusion of a brochure in AIAS's magazine and its appearance on the cover of the same publication, reaching approximately 2,000 professionals in the industry. Additionally, news about RESINSURF have been shared during key events such as BIEMH (Bilbao, Spain) and Advanced Factories (Madrid, Spain), extending the reach of information to a broader audience within the sector.

The presence on social media has also been significant. Through platforms like LinkedIn and X (Twitter), updates on consortium meetings and participation in events have been shared, achieving remarkable impact. For instance, the dissemination of the first consortium meeting on LinkedIn reached over 19,000 people, demonstrating the effectiveness of social media in connecting with the industrial and academic community.

In summary, the communication actions undertaken by RESINSURF in 2024 have been strategic in promoting sustainable alternatives in the surface treatment industry, raising awareness of the risks associated with Cr(VI), and encouraging the adoption of safer and more environmentally friendly technologies.

2.2. Summary of main activities in 2024

In order to simplify the presentation of the main communication activities of 2024, we have classified them considering the 5 communication objectives described in section 1 (Table 1).

2.2.1. Objective 1: Raising awareness on the environmental impact of electrochemical processes implying toxic substances such as Cr(VI) or critical raw materials. (+ RESINSURF’s strategy)

RESINSURF’S WEBPAGE

The RESINSURF project benefits greatly from having a dedicated webpage hosted on the Interreg SUDOE platform. This official project page offers high visibility within the SUDOE community and beyond, ensuring that our activities, results, and news reach a wide and relevant audience. The platform is specifically designed to support communication and dissemination for all Interreg SUDOE projects, providing a trusted and centralized space that stakeholders, partners, and the general public can easily access. The webpage is regularly updated to keep content current and engaging, maximizing transparency and impact. Leveraging this well-established channel not only fulfils program requirements but also strengthens our project’s credibility and transnational outreach.

During this first period, the main sections of the RESINSURF project webpage have been completed. Additionally, updates with news related to the project’s strategy have been published, aimed at engaging and reaching relevant stakeholders and general public. These efforts have ensured that the webpage remains a dynamic and informative resource, supporting effective communication throughout the project’s development.

In CIDETEC’s webpage there is also a landing page exclusively [for RESINSURF](#), and other beneficiaries of the project publish news on RESINSURF in their own webpages.

Figure 1: Screenshot of AIAS and TITANIA’s webpages explaining on RESINSURF’s project.

YOUTUBE

During 2024, a [pre-promotional video](#) was prepared and published on YouTube while a more professional version was being finalized. Rather than waiting for the final video, the pre-promotional version was actively promoted, including at a relevant fair, to ensure early visibility and engagement with stakeholders. This approach allowed the project to start building awareness and interest from the outset.

Figure 2: Screenshot of the early promotional video for the project.

The RESINSURF early promotional video serves as an introductory presentation of the project, highlighting its main objectives and the broader context in which it operates. It begins by introducing RESINSURF as a European initiative co-financed by the Interreg SUDOE Programme through the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF). The video emphasizes the urgent need for alternative, environmentally friendly surface treatment technologies and the importance of modernizing and digitally transforming industrial processes. Throughout the video, the project's commitment to making the surface treatment industry more resilient, intelligent, sustainable, and competitive is clearly conveyed. The visual identity of the project is showcased with engaging graphics and branding elements, making the message accessible and appealing. To increase the dynamism of the video, some clips of the main beneficiary's facilities (CIDETEC's) have been inserted. Additionally, the video is presented in English, Portuguese, French and Spanish to reach a wider audience across the SUDOE region. Overall, this video effectively communicates the essence and ambitions of RESINSURF, serving as a valuable tool for early outreach and stakeholder engagement while the more detailed professional video is being finalized.

WEBINARS (+ YOUTUBE)

Figure 3: Screenshots of the REACH + RESINSURF’s webinar

The [first RESINSURF webinar](#) was organized by AIAS (project beneficiary), CIDETEC (main beneficiary), and RAMBOLL (associated partner), bringing together key expertise from the consortium. RAMBOLL led the section on REACH regulations, providing valuable insights on compliance, regulatory impact, and practical information highly relevant for companies in the surface treatment sector—an audience that showed strong interest due to the direct implications for their operations. CIDETEC presented the RESINSURF project, outlining its objectives and proposed solutions for transitioning to sustainable surface treatments (REACH-compliant). The collaboration between these organizations ensured that the webinar addressed both regulatory challenges and innovative project developments, making it a highly engaging and useful event for industry stakeholders. The webinar has been uploaded to AIAS’s youtube with subtitles in Spanish.

SOCIAL MEDIA

In 2024, RESINSURF maintained an active presence on LinkedIn and X (formerly Twitter), using both platforms to share project updates, promote events, and engage directly with the professional and industrial community. Through regular posts and interactions, the project reached large companies, SMEs, business associations, and sector stakeholders, leveraging the networking strengths of LinkedIn and the real-time visibility and engagement opportunities of X. This strategy ensured that news about RESINSURF’s activities (e.g. webinars and

meetings), achievements, and participation in key events was widely disseminated, helping to build a strong online community and increase awareness among relevant audiences.

Figure 4: Screenshots of RESINSURF-related publications in Linked In from consortium entities and individuals(e.g. Jean Charles DUPIN from the beneficiary UPPA).

FAIRS

RESINSURF had a notable presence at two of the most important industrial fairs in southern Europe: [Advanced Factories Barcelona 2024](#) and [BIEMH 2024 in Bilbao](#). Advanced Factories, held from April 9 to 11, 2024, at Fira Barcelona, brought together over 27,000 professionals and more than 380 exhibitors to showcase the latest innovations in automation, robotics, artificial intelligence, and Industry 4.0 technologies. This event provided RESINSURF with an excellent platform to present its objectives and solutions to a highly specialized audience seeking advanced technologies to boost industrial productivity and sustainability. At BIEMH 2024, one of the world’s leading multisector industrial trade fairs, RESINSURF engaged with industry leaders and stakeholders interested in cutting-edge surface treatment and coating technologies. With over 1,300 exhibitors and a focus on machinery, automation, and digitalization, the fair served as an ideal venue to highlight RESINSURF’s innovative approach to sustainable and intelligent electrochemical surface treatments. Participation in both events significantly increased the project’s visibility, fostered connections with potential partners, and facilitated direct communication with companies and professionals most affected by the sector’s technological and regulatory transformation.

Figure 5: Pictures illustrating the presence of RESINSURF in the Professional Fair Advanced Factories Barcelona 2024. The early-promotional video and the new RESINSURF’s information brochure were presented.

In order to increase the visibility of the project in (but not just) fairs, a brochure, roll up and tryptic were designed and printed.

Figure 6: Design of the Roll Up (left) and the tryptic flyer (right) of the project.

PROFESSIONAL PRESS ARTICLES

The primary target audience for these communication activities includes large companies and SMEs, chambers of commerce, and business associations. To reach this audience, the project leveraged the newsletter and the specialized magazine “Ingeniería de Superficies,” published by the Surface Finishing Industries Association (AIAS), beneficiary of RESINSURF’s project. This channel ensures broad dissemination, as it is distributed to around 2,000 members who all receive both the magazine and the newsletters. AIAS and its publication maintain a strong presence at major industry trade fairs, further amplifying their reach.

Figure 6. Two examples of articles on RESINSURF in the “Ingeniería de Superficies” AIAS’s magazine. Left: Presence of RESINSURF in BIEMH 2024. Right: Presence of RESINSURF in Advanced Factories Barcelona 2024.

During this period, RESINSURF was featured on the cover of “Ingeniería de Superficies” No. 140 (July 2024). The magazine included dedicated articles on RESINSURF’s participation at key events such as the Advanced Factories Barcelona 2024 (page 37) and the BIEMH 2024 trade fair in Bilbao (page 42). Additionally, an informational brochure about RESINSURF was distributed alongside the magazine at BIEMH 2024, as highlighted in the corresponding article. The project’s presence at BIEMH 2024 was also announced through the AIAS newsletter, ensuring that the information reached the entire network of industry professionals and stakeholders associated with AIAS.

Relevant organizations and media outlets, such as [SPRI](#) and [INTEREMPRESAS](#), have featured the RESINSURF project in their publications, highlighting its innovative approach and impact within the surface treatment industry, as well as [promoting](#) some of its activities.

Figure 7. Screenshots of 2 examples of the impact of RESINSURF, featured in on-line news from INTEREMPRESAS and SPRI.

PRESS ADVERTISEMENTS

RESINSURF has also been promoted through advertisements in professional press specialized in the surface finishing industry. These advertisements have appeared in key sector magazines and journals, reaching a targeted audience of industry professionals, companies, and decision-makers. By placing ads in well-established publications, RESINSURF ensures visibility among stakeholders who are directly involved in surface treatment processes and are interested in sustainable and regulatory-compliant innovations. This presence in the professional press complements other communication channels, reinforcing the project’s outreach and impact within the industrial community.

Figure 7. Screenshot of a double page for the professional magazine “Técnica y tecnología para tratamientos térmicos y de superficies” from INTEREMPRESAS, showing (right) an advertisement on RESINSURF project.

2.2.2. Objective 2: Disseminating the advances of the pilots.

RESINSURF’S WEBPAGE

The RESINSURF project webpage includes information about the two Pilots underway as well as news on the latest advancements related to these pilots. It highlights the development of new, safer surface treatment technologies designed to replace hexavalent chromium, focusing on two pilot projects that are being tested and scaled up in real industrial environments. Updates on progress, such as the recent scaling up of the hard chrome pilot by CIDETEC, are regularly shared to keep stakeholders informed about the technological developments and practical implementation steps. This ongoing communication ensures transparency and engagement with companies and professionals interested in sustainable and regulatory-compliant surface treatments.

Figure 8: Screenshots of RESINSURF’s webpage, showing the links and sections for each Pilot, along with a map with the location of the validation facilities for the pilots.

Figure 9: Screenshots of RESINSURF’s webpage, showing the links and sections to various RESINSURF-related news. On the right, detail of one of the news, related to advances in Pilot 1.

OTHER WEBPAGES (BENEFICIARIES)

11 meses después del inicio del proyecto RESINSURF

11/12/2024

Después de meses de trabajo, el proyecto RESINSURF sigue su curso gracias al trabajo del consorcio. En esta ocasión, nos centramos en compartir los avances de las pruebas piloto 2 donde Titania centra sus esfuerzos.

Esta fase consiste en la validación a nivel de planta piloto del proceso de sustitución de cromo hexavalente (Cr VI) en la protección de aleaciones ligeras, junto con la implementación y validación de diferentes sistemas de control y monitorización del proceso.

En concreto, durante esta etapa se pretende verificar la transferibilidad de las soluciones tecnológicas adoptadas en otras aplicaciones que incluyen anodizado, deposición de capas de conversión y deposición electroférica de pintura sobre aleaciones ligeras. Para ello, en un principio, Titania iba a adquirir un cromatógrafo para analizar y cuantificar la evolución de los compuestos volátiles de la pintura a emplear para los recubrimientos anafóricos. Sin embargo, se ha optado por no adquirir el equipo y colaborar con la Universidad de Cádiz quien posee recursos expertos en la materia. Es decir, la Universidad de Cádiz cuenta con un grupo de investigación especializado en "Estructura y Química de Nanomateriales" con conocimientos y experiencia en la aplicación de técnicas para las que se emplea el cromatógrafo. Con esta decisión, se estrechan lazos y se fomenta la transferencia de conocimiento entre universidad y empresa.

Paralelamente, también en esta etapa del proyecto, Titania se encuentra en fase de adquisición de fungibles como:

- ✓ La materia prima, en especial, las chapas de aluminio y la laca y los bastidores que se emplearán en los procesos químicos.
- ✓ Productos químicos para los baños y la laca para el proceso anafórico.

Figure 10: Screenshot of TITANIA's webpage explaining on Pilot 2 (which the entity will validate in its facilities).

SOCIAL MEDIA

In 2024, RESINSURF actively used LinkedIn and X (formerly Twitter) to share updates specifically on the advancement of its pilot projects and to showcase preliminary results. Regular posts highlighted key milestones, such as the scaling up of the hard chrome pilot, and provided insights into the transition of new technologies from laboratory to industrial conditions. By sharing these developments, RESINSURF kept large companies, SMEs, business associations, and other stakeholders informed about the real-world progress and early successes of its safer, eco-friendly surface treatment alternatives. This approach generated strong interest and

RESINSURF

engagement from the professional community, reinforcing the project’s visibility and impact within the sector.

Figure 11: Screenshots of RESINSURF’s publications in Linked In on advances in Pilot development and validation. Left: Pilot 1. Right: Pilot 2.

2.2.3. Objective 3: Disseminating the scientific results of the pilots.

It was not yet possible to disseminate final results from RESINSURF during this period, as the project was still in its early stages. However, some preliminary findings were shared at major conferences such as ECHT2024 and A3TS 2024 in Toulouse, where CIDETEC and INEOSURF presented initial outcomes from RESINSURF predecessor projects that have informed its development. This allowed the project to contribute to sector discussions while full results are still being generated.

Figure 11: Linked In screenshots on a publication showing the presence of RESINSURF in the ECHT2024 congress.

2.3. Record of all the activities in 2024

The previous section was showing a summary of the most representative communication activities of the project. All the communication activities held during 2024 are presented in Table 2. The table specifies the type of activity (along with a short description), the date and project month of execution, the main responsible(s), place, target groups and estimated reach, along with a link to the activity, when possible.

RESINSURF

TABLE 2: Record of RESINSURF’s communication activities conducted during 2024

Type of Activity	Short description	Date	M	RESPONSIBLE	Place	Target Group /s reached	Number of people reached	Link (if existent)	NOTES
a) Media based activity (newspapers, specialist magazines, news agencies, press releases...)									
Brochure in magazine	GT1 - Brochure DinA4 included in the AIAS's magazine (printed version).	06/06/2024	M6	AIAS +CIDETEC	AIAS's magazine	3,4,5	2000	HERE	
Magazine cover	GT1 - Cover of the AIAS journal	M7	M7	AIAS	AIAS's magazine	3,4,5	2000	HERE	r
Magazine	GT1 - News on Resinsurf in BIEMH	M7	M7	AIAS	AIAS's magazine	3,4,5	2000	HERE	P. 42
Magazine	GT1 - News on Resinsurf in Advanced factories	M7	M7	AIAS	AIAS's magazine	3,4,5	2000	HERE	P. 47
b) Internet-based activities (specify if Website, Newsletter, Social media, on-line editorials...)									
Social media	GTT - Difussion RESINSURF 1st consortium meeting	28/03/2024	M3	CIDETEC	LinkedIn (CIDETEC)	3,5	21700	HERE	
Social media	GTT - Difussion RESINSURF 1st consortium meeting	27/03/2024	M3	CIDETEC	Twitter (CIDETEC)	Industry	2200	HERE	
Social media	GTT - Difussion RESINSURF 1st consortium meeting	M3	M3	AIAS	LinkedIn (AIAS)	3,4,5	610	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - Difussion RESINSURF at ADVANCED FACTORIES BARCELONA	12/04/2024	M4	AIAS	LinkedIn (AIAS)	3,4,5	610	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - Difussion RESINSURF at ADVANCED FACTORIES BARCELONA	19/04/2024	M4	CIDETEC	LinkedIn (CIDETEC)	3,5	21700	HERE	
Social media	GTT - Difussion RESINSURF at SUDOE Santander Seminar	19/04/2024	M4	CIDETEC	LinkedIn (CIDETEC)	3,5	21700	HERE	
Social media	GTT - Difussion RESINSURF at SUDOE Santander Seminar	19/04/2024	M4	CIDETEC	Twitter (CIDETEC)	3,5	2200	HERE	

RESINSURF

COMMUNICATION REPORT

Social media	GT1 - Pre-difussion of RESINSURF at BIEMH, Bilbao.	30/05/2024	M5	AIAS	LinkedIn (AIAS)	3,4,5	610	HERE	
Youtube video	GT1 - Pre-promotional video of the Project But it was also shared via social media, webpage and fairs / we already have a new professional video (2025)	31/05/2024	M5	AIAS + CIDETEC	YOUTUBE (AIAS)	3,4,5	32	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - Pre-difussion of RESINSURF at BIEMH, Bilbao.	M6	M6	AIAS	LinkedIn (AIAS)	3,4,5	610	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - News RESINSURF at BIEMH, Bilbao.	M6	M6	AIAS	LinkedIn (AIAS)	3,4,5	610	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - Difussion of RESINSURF at BIEMH, Bilbao.	06/06/2024	M6	CIDETEC	LinkedIn (CIDETEC)	3,5	21700	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - Difussion of RESINSURF at BIEMH, Bilbao.	06/06/2024	M6	CIDETEC	Twitter (CIDETEC)	3,5	2200	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - Difussion of RESINSURF at ECHT 2024, Toulouse.	10/06/2024	M6	CIDETEC	LinkedIn (CIDETEC)	3,5	21700	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - Difussion of RESINSURF at ECHT 2024, Toulouse.	10/06/2024	M6	CIDETEC	Twitter (CIDETEC)	3,5	2200	HERE	
Webpage news	GT1 - News on RESINSURF project at TITANIA's webpage	14/06/2024	M6	TITANIA	Web page (TITANIA)	3,5	2000	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - Difussion of news on RESINSURF project at TITANIA's webpage	05/07/2024	M7	TITANIA	LinkedIn (TITANIA)	3,5	2450	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - Difussion of news on RESINSURF project at TITANIA's SM	05/07/2024	M7	TITANIA	Instagram (TITANIA)	1,3,5,7	>270	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - Difussion of news on RESINSURF project at TITANIA's SM	05/07/2024	M7	TITANIA	Twitter(TITANIA)	3,5	-	X	Account cancel.
Webpage link	GT1/2/3 - Permanent link of RESINSURF's SUDOE webpage in AIAS webpage	M7	M7	AIAS	Web page (AIAS)	3,4,5	>130	HERE	
Newsletter	GT1 - AIAS newsletter 66 (on-line) - On RESINSURF's presence in BIEMH	M7	M7	AIAS	Web page (AIAS)	3,4,5	>130	HERE	
Webpage minisite	GT1/2/3 - Minisite on RESINSURF in CIDETEC's webpage	08/07/2024	M7	CIDETEC	Web page (CIDETEC)	3,5	>130	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - Promo revista AIAS con RESINSURF en la portada	M7	M7	AIAS	LinkedIn (AIAS)	3,4,5	610	HERE	

Webpage news (IMPACT)	GT1 - Promo RESINSURF	30/07/2024	M7	Parke (IMPACT)	WebPage(PARKE)	1,2,3,4,5,6,7	-	HERE
Webpage (IMPACT)	GT1 - Promo RESINSURF	29/07/2024	M7	Industria Química	Webpage (Industria Química)	3,4,5	-	HERE
Social media (IMPACT)	GT1 - News on RESINSURF	M8	M8	IMHE (IMPACT)	Linkedin (Revista Tecnologías de Fabricación IMHE)	3,5	5500	HERE
Social media (IMPACT)	GT1 - News on RESINSURF	M8	M8	Estrategia.net (IMPACT)	X (Estrategia.net)	3,4,5,6,7	3600	HERE
Social media (IMPACT)	GT1 - News on RESINSURF	M8	M8	Izaro Manufacturing Technology (IMPACT)	X (Izaro Manufacturing Technology, IMPACT)	3,4,5,6	1600	HERE
Webpage news (IMPACT)	GT1 - Publication of news on RESINSURF in INTEREMPRESAS webpage	04/09/2024	M9	Interempresas (IMPACT)	Interempresas WebPage	3,4,5	462	HERE
Social media (IMPACT)	GT1 - News on RESINSURF	12/09/2024	M9	Pedecapress (IMPACT)	X (Pedecapress, IMPACT)	3,4,5	398	HERE
Social media (IMPACT)	GT1 - News on RESINSURF en BIEHM	04/09/2024	M9	Interempresas (IMPACT)	X (Interempresas, IMPACT)	3,4,5	52	HERE
Social media (IMPACT)	GT1 - News on RESINSURF	04/09/2024	M9	Interempresas (IMPACT)	X (Interempresas, IMPACT)	3,4,5	52	HERE

RESINSURF

COMMUNICATION REPORT

Social media (IMPACT)	GT1 - News on RESINSURF	06/09/2024	M9	Agencia de Noticias (IMPACT)	X (Agencia de Noticias, IMPACT)	3,4,5,7	12200	HERE	
Webpage (IMPACT)	GT1 - News on RESINSURF	06/09/2024	M9	Agencia de Noticias (IMPACT)	Webpage (Agencia de Noticias, IMPACT)	3,4,5,7	-	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - News on Project RESINSURF	M9	M9	SPRI (IMPACT)	LinkedIn (SPRI)	1,2,3,4,5,6	22000	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - News on Project RESINSURF	M9	M9	SPRI (IMPACT)	X (SPRI)	1,2,3,4,5,6	11200	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - Promo Minisite on RESINSURF in CIDETEC webpage	M9	M9	CIDETEC	LinkedIn(CI DETEC)	3,5	21700	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - Promo Minisite on RESINSURF in CIDETEC webpage	M9	M9	CIDETEC	X(CIDETEC)	3,5	2200	HERE	
Newsletter (IMPACT)	GT1 - Newsletter on RESINSURF from Grupo Spri Agencia Vasca de Desarrollo Empresarial	06/09/2024	M9	SPRI (IMPACT)	Newsletter and webpage Grupo Spri Agencia Vasca de Desarrollo Empresarial	1,2,3,4,5,6	-	HERE	
Webpage news (IMPACT)	GT1 - Noticia: El proyecto RESINSURF desarrolla alternativas sostenibles para sustituir el cromo hexavalente	06/09/2024	M9	MMA Ingeniería (IMPACT)	Webpage MMA INGENIERIA (IMPACT)	3,5,6	-	HERE	-
Webpage news (IMPACT)	GT1 - Promo RESINSURF	06/09/2024	M9	GIPUZKOA GAUR (IMPACT)	Webpage GIPUZKOA GAUR (IMPACT)	7	-	HERE	
Webpage news (IMPACT)	GT1 - Promo RESINSURF	25/09/2024	M9	ADEGI (IMPACT)	Webpage ADEGI (IMPACT)	3,5,6	-	HERE	-

Social media	GTT - News on RESINSURF 2nd Consortium meeting	07/10/2024	M10	CIDETEC	LinkedIn (CIDETEC)	3,5	21700	HERE	
Social media	GTT - News on RESINSURF 2nd Consortium meeting	07/10/2024	M10	CIDETEC	Twitter (CIDETEC)	3,5	2200	HERE	
Webpage news	GTT - News on RESINSURF 2nd Consortium meeting	M10	M10	AIAS	Web page (AIAS)	3,4,5	>130	HERE	
Social media	GTT - News on RESINSURF 2nd Consortium meeting	M10	M10	AIAS	LinkedIn (AIAS)	3,4,5	610	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - Difussion/post about webinar 6thNovember	04/11/2024	M11	AIAS	LinkedIn (AIAS)	3,4,5	610	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - Difussion/post about webinar 6thNovember	05/11/2024	M11	TITANIA	LinkedIn (TITANIA)	3,5	2450	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - Difussion/post about webinar 6thNovember	05/11/2024	M11	TITANIA	Instagram (TITANIA)	1,3,5,7	>270	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - Difussion/post about webinar 6thNovember	05/11/2024	M11	TITANIA	Twitter(TITANIA)	3,5	-	X	Account cancel.
Social media	GT1 - News webinar 6thNovember	11/11/2024	M11	CIDETEC	LinkedIn(CIDETEC)	3,5	21700	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - News webinar 6thNovember	11/11/2024	M11	CIDETEC	X(CIDETEC)	3,5	2200	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - Post about webinar in AIAS's webpage	07/11/2024	M11	TITANIA	LinkedIn (TITANIA)	3,5	2450	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - Post about webinar in AIAS's webpage	07/11/2024	M11	TITANIA	Twitter(TITANIA)	3,5	-	X	Account cancel.
Social media (IMPACT)	CC - Post about SUDOE communication webinar and RESINSURF's participation	M11	M11	HENKO (SUDOE)(IMPACT)	Linkedin (Personal)	1,7	>500	HERE	
Social media (IMPACT)	CC - Post about SUDOE communication webinar and RESINSURF's participation	M11	M11	SUDOE(IMPACT)	X(SUDOE)	1,3,5,7	2977	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - Promo of Survey	M11	M11	CIDETEC	LinkedIn(CIDETEC)	3,5	21700	HERE	

Social media	GT1 - Promo of Survey	M11	M11	CIDETEC	X(CIDETEC)	3,5	2200	HERE	
Webpage news	GT2 - Pilot 2 implementation in TITANIA	11/12/2024	M12	TITANIA	Web page (TITANIA)	3,5	2000	HERE	
Social media	GT2 - Difussion/post pilot 2	17/12/2024	M12	TITANIA	LinkedIn (TITANIA)	3,5	2450	HERE	
Social media	GT2 - Difussion/post pilot 2	17/12/2024	M12	TITANIA	Instagram (TITANIA)	1,3,5,7	>270	HERE	
Newsletter (IMPACT)	GT1 - Promo RESINSURF	M12	M12	EFC (IMPACT)	Newsletter (EFC)	Industry	-	HERE	P.23
Social media	GT1 - Promo RESINSURF in EFC newsletter	M12	M12	CIDETEC	LinkedIn(CIDETEC)	3,5	21700	HERE	
Social media	GT1 - Promo RESINSURF in EFC newsletter	M12	M12	CIDETEC	X(CIDETEC)	3,5	2200	HERE	
Webpage minisite	GT1/2/3 - Minisite on RESINSURF in IPREM-UPPA's webpage	?	?	UPPA	Minisite (UPPA)	1,3,7	-	HERE	
News Resinsurf webpabe	GT1 - On RESINSURF	02/09/2024	M9	CIDETEC	Resinsurf webpage	1,2,3,4,5,6,7	-	HERE	
News Resinsurf webpabe	GT1 - 2nd Consortium Meeting	07/10/2024	M10	CIDETEC	Resinsurf webpage	1,2,3,4,5,6,7	-	HERE	
News Resinsurf webpabe	GT2 - Pilot 1	25/10/2024	M10	CIDETEC	Resinsurf webpage	1,2,3,4,5,6,7	-	HERE	
c) In person (specify if participation in an event, presentation of the project at an event, B2B meeting, etc.)									
Fair (AIAS)	GT1 - Difussion of RESINSURF at ADVANCED FACTORIES BARCELONA	8-10/04/2024	M4	AIAS	Advanced Factories Barcelona	1,2,3,4,5,6	380 exhibitors and aprox 20,000 attendees	HERE	
Fair (AIAS + CIDETEC)	GT1 - Difussion of RESINSURF at BIEMH, Bilbao.	3-7/05/2024	M5	AIAS + CIDETEC	BIEMH 2024	3,4,5,6	> 35000 visitors, >1400 exhibitors	HERE	

Conferences (CIDETEC + INEOSURF)	GT1/2 - PPT presentation of RESINSURF (fundaments and first results), Toulouse.	5-7/06/2024	M6	CIDETEC + INEOSURF	ECHT 2024 + A3TS 2024	1,2,3,4,5,6	350 delegates and 1,000 visit.; 90.conferences	HERE	
Fair (AIAS)	GT1 - Difussion of RESINSURF at Advanced Manufacturing Madrid, con RollUp	5-6/12/2024	M12	AIAS	ADVANCED Manufactur es Madrid	3,4,5,6	>620 expositors, 13500 attendees	HERE	
d) Other type of dissemination activities									
Posters	RESINSURF poster (official)	From M6	From M6	ALL	One per partner (visible place)	1,2,3,4,5,6,7		HERE	
Tryptic 01	Tryptic introducing RESINSURF project and its strategy	From M9	From M9	CIDETEC	Events, meetings...	1,2,3,4,5,6,7		HERE	
Roll up	Roll up of the project	From M9	From M9	CIDETEC	Fairs, congresses , open days...	1,2,3,4,5,6,7		HERE	
Brochure	Roll up of the project	From M6	From M7	AIAS	Fairs, congresses , open days...	1,2,3,4,5,6,8		HERE	

3. Conclusions

In 2024, RESINSURF's communication activities successfully established the project's visibility and engagement across multiple channels, including its dedicated webpage, professional press, industry fairs, social media platforms, and specialized webinars. The project's presence at major events such as Advanced Factories Barcelona and BIEMH 2024, along with features in sector magazines and newsletters, ensured that key stakeholders-ranging from large companies and SMEs to business associations-were kept informed about the project's objectives, pilot developments, and early advancements. Social media outreach on LinkedIn and X further amplified these messages, while targeted webinars and articles addressed the regulatory context and the project's innovative approach.

As the pilots progress, 2025 will mark a shift in focus towards disseminating concrete results from these pilot projects and sharing validated outcomes with the industry. Additionally, communication efforts will increasingly support GT3 activities, emphasizing training and capacity-building to prepare companies and professionals for the adoption of safer and more sustainable surface treatment technologies. This evolving strategy will ensure that RESINSURF not only informs but also empowers the sector to implement the project's innovations.